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Sin and Guilt

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Editorial

It is undeniable that notions of sin and guilt play a significant role in human life and human thought. That is why we have chosen sin and guilt as the theme of this issue of *Jnanadeepa*.

In order to gain a broader understanding of sin and guilt we shall discuss them from interdisciplinary perspectives. We shall not only examine the meaning sin and guilt have in different traditions and disciplines but also investigate the role they play in different world-views.

There is an article in this issue which seeks to develop psychological perspectives on sin and guilt. For a long time most psychologists were reluctant to explore sin since it seemed to be closely related to religion and theology. In recent years a number of psychologists have been showing some interest in the study of sin. Guilt is a favourite theme in psychoanalysis. It is true that an exaggerated sense of guilt can lead to depression. And yet the lack of a sense of guilt can result in the formation of an antisocial personality. But a healthy sense of guilt has many pro-social benefits.

Another article deals with the meaning and function of sin in the Islamic world-view. The Islamic concept of sin is similar to the Jewish view. Islam sees sin as anything that goes against the will of God. Words like transgression and disobedience are also used to denote sin. Islam also deals with repentance and forgiveness of sin. Repentance is more than asking for God's forgiveness, it is turning to God with sincere love and devotion. For the Moslems Allah is merciful forgiving. But he is also a judge who punishes. In Islam offences against human beings are regarded as offences against God. Hence it is necessary to repent of one's sins before God and offer compensation to the injured party. Islam teaches that human relations should be based on love and forgiveness. It also calls for forgiveness of one's enemies.

Yet another article seeks to articulate a functional approach to the Christian doctrine of sin. It endeavours to answer the question: what specific function does the doctrine of sin fulfil in the Christian religion?

The article asserts that the function of sin is to reveal the human person to himself / herself by offering a mirror image of the person. It reveals the disfigurement and disintegration of the person that result from sin. From this understanding of the function of sin the article draws some valuable conclusions for theology and Christian living.

Included in this issue is an article which discusses the understanding of sin in the Theology of Karl Rahner. Rahner's notion of sin is based on his understanding of the human person. Human persons are creatures of God who are dependent on God for their being and final fulfilment. At the same time, they are endowed with true and radical freedom so that they can accept or reject God's offer of communion and eternal bliss. In the last analysis, our exercise of freedom is either a self-realization in the direction of God or a radical self-refusal towards God. Herein lies the possibility of sin. In the Christian scheme of things, sin has to be seen in the context of God's offer of forgiving love.

There is another article in this issue which discusses the notion of good and evil in tribal societies. The tribal approach to good and evil is based on concrete life experiences. Thus the idea of good is inseparably tied up with what is good for the tribal people in the physical order of the world. They experience happiness in good health, sufficient wealth, good crops, many cattle and children with whom the performance of ritual offerings to God and the ancestor spirits is guaranteed. For the well-being of humans depends on the good pleasure of these supernatural beings. For the tribal people, evil is physical suffering such as sickness, death, the loss of livestock and property. They have an understanding of moral evil. An action is judged to be right or wrong in reference to the good of the individual and all the members of the community. Tribal morality places great emphasis on the community and the tribe. The goal of life is the good of the community and the continuity of the tribe, for herein lies the good of one and all.

Included in this issue is an article on sin in some contemporary western philosophers. It deals mainly with some existentialist and postmodernist thinkers. Thus for Albert Camus sin is to turn one's back on the struggle against injustice, hypocrisy and tyranny. For Sartre sin is bad faith, that is, insincerity or hypocrisy. It is to abdicate the demands of the responsibility of one's freedom and to trot out all manner of excuses to cover up one's cowardice. But the great 'sin' that

postmodernism lays bare is what we might call 'structural sin': those unjust structures and false values upon which international and intra-national networks are built and which serve as effective brakes on the development of the oppressed peoples, ensuring that the dominant groups maintain successfully their stranglehold on world economy and culture.

There are two articles in this issue which are not directly related to our main theme. The first one deals with human dignity and the freedom of research. After a lengthy discussion of the different aspects of human embryonic stem cells research, the article examines the ethical issues involved in it. It maintains that using embryos for any purpose other than to allow it grow into babies is highly controversial and unethical. It is a violation of human dignity. Destroying a human embryo in order to provide a cure for a disease is wholly unacceptable because it is morally evil.

The second deals with Catholic colleges and social transformation. It calls into question the conventional view that education can bring about a significant change in the consciousness of a society, which in turn can transform its social, economic and political structures. It also disagrees with the opposite view that education does not, indeed cannot, transform society. The article favours a third view which holds that, while education as a process of socialization tends to make individuals conform to the norms and values of the existing society, thus dominating and domesticating them, it has the capacity to generate a spirit of inquiry and questioning of accepted truths and values, thereby leading to a change in society. It also spells out some of the ways in which Catholic colleges can contribute to social transformation.

Kurien Kunnumpuram, SJ
(Editor)